

The ear canal is neither a cylinder nor a horn: What are the acoustical consequences?

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Abstract.

This work aims to explore how ear-canal geometry affects audiometric and experimental measurements. Advances in CT technology and software enable a detailed understanding of ear-canal geometry from infancy to old age. There is substantial variability among individuals in both (1) the area at specific canal locations and (2) changes in areas and curvature along the canal. This work focuses on anatomical and acoustical measurements of ears aged 40-50 years. Anatomical measurements derived from CT scans are discussed first, followed by absorbance measurements taken from 3D-printed canal replicas connected to an artificial ear. Contrary to previous assumptions, absorbance varies with canal geometry, with the anatomically-derived 3D-printed canals showing greater variations along the canal compared to the 3D-printed cylindrical canal. These findings highlight the need for further exploration into how individual ear-canal geometry impacts the acoustics within the canal in general and more specifically the calculation of absorbance, which is defined in terms of the canal's cross-sectional area.

INTRODUCTION

Ongoing work [1, 2] demonstrates a wide range of canal areas and curvatures and suggests that the cross-sectional area at and lateral to the first bend increases with age throughout the human lifespan, as illustrated by our preliminary and yet-to-be-published measurements (Fig. 1). In contrast, FDA-approved measurement systems for wideband acoustic immittance (WAI) assume circular cross-sectional canal areas, with probe tip areas of 44 – 50 mm² in adults and about 17 mm² in infants [3, 4]. However, Fig. 1 challenges this assumption by showing areas at the first bend (0 mm in Fig. 1) ranging from nearly half to close to three times the assumed areas. Furthermore, the acoustical effects of area changes along the canal, including both increases and decreases, have not been considered.

This work is presented in two parts. First, we report detailed anatomical results from CT scans of 20 ears (ages 40-49 years), including area changes along the entire canal length, canal curvature, and bone-to-cartilage-transition locations. Second, absorbance was measured within 3D-printed ear canal replicas coupled to an artificial ear; results are reported for three of the ears whose anatomical measurements were also made.

ANATOMICAL CANAL GEOMETRY MEASUREMENTS

Methods: Subjects, CT scans, definitions, and methodology

We analyzed high-resolution de-identified CT scans from 20 adults aged 40-49 years to obtain canal area and geometry measurements. Exemptions from Institutional Review Board oversight were granted by both the University of Massachusetts Chan Medical School (where the CT scans originated) and Smith College (where the research was conducted) due to the retrospective and de-identified nature of the work. Using OsiriX MD software (Pixmeo, Version 13.0.2), systematic measurements were taken along each canal, including: (a) *Location and area of the canal termination*, defined by the plane that intersects the bony tympanic annulus, (b) *Canal central axis*, defined in 3D space as the curved spline following the center of the canal from its entrance to its termination, (c) *Canal cross-sectional area*, defined as the area within the plane perpendicular to the canal wall at each measurement location, (d) *Canal entrance*, defined as the most lateral position where the plane normal to the canal wall is fully enclosed by the canal, (e) *The first bend of the canal*, determined as the lateral-most position with the largest canal curvature near the first bend as viewed on the CT scan.

FIGURE 1. Preliminary and ongoing measurements (not yet published) from CT scans of cross-sectional areas along the ear canal of subjects ranging in age from 6 months to 91 years. The measurements are referenced to the first bend of the canal, defined as a distance of zero mm; negative distances are medial to the first bend toward the tympanic annulus and positive distances are lateral to the first bend toward the canal entrance. Thin lines are individual measurements, thick lines are means, and error bars are standard errors. The measurement methodology is described by Balouch et al. [1] and preliminary results were presented at the 2023 American Auditory Society Meeting [5]. We note that the measurement resolution was 2 mm for medial parts of the canal and 1 mm near and lateral to the first bend location; in order to reference the area measurements to the first bend, we interpolated measurements with a 2 mm resolution to a 1 mm resolution.

The methods for these measurements are outlined by Balouch et al. (2023) [1], who also demonstrated that the left and right canal areas and geometries within a subject are notably more similar than those across subjects. Measurements were taken at 2 mm intervals, commencing at the tympanic annulus and shifting to 1 mm intervals either at 24 mm from the tympanic annulus or within a few mm of the first bend, whichever occurred first. A new methodological feature introduced here is the ability to plot the canal's central axis in 3D space, enabling the calculation of the spatial derivative to objectively determine curvature for identifying the location of the first bend. Another addition is the measurement of the location where the canal transitions from bone to cartilage. Measurements along the axis documented the transition from bone (closer to the annulus) to cartilage (more lateral locations) for the canal-wall positions superior, anterior, inferior, and posterior, referenced to the orientation of the subject in the scanner. The resolution of these measurements is 2 mm, based on the resolution of the canal-area measurements and the location of the bone-to-cartilage transition.

Results and Discussion: Anatomical Canal Geometry Measurements

Figure 2 presents the canal geometry measurements for 20 individual subjects. Panels A and B depict the canal cross-sectional areas along the canal length, referenced to the center of the tympanic annulus (panel A) and to the location of the first bend (panel B). There is notable variability across subjects, with areas at the first bend ranging from 25 to 90 mm², first bend locations ranging from 22 to 30 mm from the annulus, canal lengths ranging from 27 to 38 mm, and canal entrance areas ranging from 66 to 137 mm². Additionally, each canal's area fluctuates uniquely along its length, with most canals increasing in area lateral to the first bend, decreasing in area medial to the first bend for several mm, and some showing substantial increases or decreases in area between the annulus and the first bend.

Panel C summarizes the location of the bone-to-cartilage transition along the canal's central axis. Typically, the transition begins along the superior part of the canal (range 8-14 mm) and progresses through the anterior, inferior, and ultimately posterior parts of the canal (range 12-20 mm), although the sequence may deviate from this typical pattern. The length of the transition also varies among ears; while some ears fully transition within a single 2 mm measurement increment, others transition over several mm along the canal. The bone-to-cartilage transition always occurs several mm before the first bend of the canal.

Panels D through F depict representations of the spline curve defining the canal's central axis. Panel D displays the central axis in 3D space, which can be rotated for visual analysis. Panel E, the 2D projection of panel D in the inferior-to-superior dimension, demonstrates that as the canal progresses from its most medial point (0 mm) towards its lateral-most point (± 40 mm), it moves superiorly, then inferiorly, and near the first bend changes direction back to superior. Panel F, the 2D projection of panel D in the anterior-to-posterior dimension, shows the canal's movement from a more posterior position (at the annulus) to a more anterior location (at the entrance) along its length.

Figure 3 displays images from the CT scans depicting the cross-sectional area at the first bend for each ear, highlighting the variations in area and geometry among subjects. Note that the canal is typically not circular.

FIGURE 2. **A:** Canal areas from 20 ears of 20 unique individuals as a function of distance from the tympanic annulus. **B:** The same measurements as panel A except shifted so that plots are relative to the first-bend location which is defined as zero. **C:** Location of bone-to-cartilage transition at the four measured locations along the canal. **D:** Canal's central axis plotted in 3D-space for each of the 20 ears; this plot can be rotated to view at different angles. **E:** The 2D plane through the 3D plot of panel D to show the canal's curvature in the inferior-to-superior dimension. **F:** The 2D plane through the 3D plot of panel D to show the canal's curvature in the anterior-to-posterior dimension.

FIGURE 3. The MPR sagittal plane at the first bend for each of the 20 ears. The scale is the same for all images, with a measurement bar of 10 mm shown in the upper left in green.

CANAL ACOUSTICAL MEASUREMENTS

Methods: WAI measurements in 3D-printed canals coupled to an artificial ear

Figure 4 (Left) shows the experimental setup, designed to generate measurements influenced solely by the canal's geometry and probe location and independent of the impedance properties of the terminating middle ear, as the same artificial ear was employed for all measurements. WAI quantities were measured using Mimosa Acoustic's Hear-ID system [4], coupled to a 3D-printed ear canal terminated by the 3D-printed artificial ear. Fig. 4 (Right) illustrates that absorbance measurements made within a 3D-printed cylindrical canal terminated by the artificial ear yielded absorbance values similar to those obtained with the Larson Davis AEC304 Ear Simulator and lower absorbances than the mean (yet within one standard deviation) from 29 normal-hearing human ears measured by Rosowski et al. (2012) using the Hear-ID system [6]. These results suggest that the experimental platform may absorb less acoustical energy along the canal than a live ear or that our artificial ear may not represent an average ear. Nonetheless, the responses support the use of this technique for studying canal acoustics.

Eight of the canals from the previously presented 20 subjects were 3D-printed using a method outlined elsewhere [7, 8], and systematic WAI measurements were conducted at probe locations ± 3 mm from the first bend. Results from three of these ears are presented here as they collectively demonstrate many features observed across all eight canals.

FIGURE 4. Left: Hear-ID coupled to a cylindrical canal (Area=44 mm²) terminated by the artificial ear and examples of 3D-printed canals. Right: Absorbance measured using Hear-ID coupled to the cylindrical canal at indicated canal lengths and terminated with the 3D-printed Artificial Ear and the industry standard Larson Davis AEC304 Ear Simulator. The gray shaded region shows the mean \pm STD from Hear-ID measurements on 29 normal-hearing subjects measured by Rosowski et al. (2012) using the Hear-ID system [6].

Results and Discussion: WAI measurements in 3D-printed canals coupled to an artificial ear

Figure 5 plots the WAI quantities of impedance and absorbance for three subjects with the HearID probe at specified canal locations relative to the first bend. Generally, the impedance magnitude and angle exhibit predictable behavior with increasing canal length, with low frequencies dominated by compliant behavior and resonant features above 2000 Hz consistent with the acoustical behavior of a cylindrical tube terminated by a middle-ear-like impedance. However, there are also indications of behavior differing from that of a cylindrical tube. In two of the three example ears (10685 and 55), the quarter-wavelengths $\lambda/4$ associated with the impedance minima at the first-bend location predict canal lengths within about 1-2 mm of the measured first-bend location. Conversely, for Subject 10713, $\lambda/4$ is approximately 6 mm shorter than the measured first-bend location, resulting in an underestimation of the canal length by 5-7 mm, a pattern observed in four of the eight canals in which measurements were made.

FIGURE 5. WAI measurements of impedance magnitude (Upper), impedance angle (Middle), and absorbance (Lower) using three of the 3D-printed canals coupled to the artificial ear: Subject 10713 Right (Left Column), Subject 10685 Left (Middle Column), and Subject 55 Left (Right Column). Measurements were nominally made in 1 mm increments at ± 3 mm from the canal's first bend (FB), although measurements were not obtained at -3 mm for Subjects 10685 or 10713 because the probe could not make it around the entire bend. Absorbance measurements were calculated with both the instrument's default constant area of 44 mm² (solid lines) and also with the area measured from the CT scan (dashed lines, areas indicated in legends). Shown within each magnitude plot is a sketch of the 3D-printed canal where the first bend is visible. The first bends are located 28, 26, and 28 mm from the tympanic annulus for Subjects 10713, 10685, and 55 respectively.

The absorbance measurements also exhibit behaviors that are both consistent and inconsistent with the canal modeled as a cylinder. In a cylindrical canal with minimal losses and a constant area by definition, absorbance would not vary with probe location. However, all three subjects' absorbances do show variations with measurement location, particularly pronounced at 2000 Hz and higher. It remains unclear whether these probe-location effects stem from changes in canal area along the canal, curvatures of the canal, or a combination of both features. Future experiments will be designed to investigate these issues of area changes and curvature.

Another absorbance-related issue pertains to the calculation of absorbance using the characteristic impedance of the canal, defined as $Z_o = \frac{\rho c}{A}$, where ρ and c represent the density and speed of sound in air, respectively, and A denotes the constant cross-sectional area of the cylindrical tube. In theory, a tube terminated by its own characteristic impedance Z_o would generate zero reflections and absorb all acoustic energy. However, our application of transmission line theory to ear-canal-based acoustical measurements has not adequately addressed how to define and interpret the canal's characteristic impedance when the area changes along its length. Questions arise as to whether the characteristic impedance corresponds to the area at the probe location, some average of the area along the canal, or if it is even meaningful to define a characteristic impedance in this context.

In Figure 5 (lower plots), absorbance was calculated with both the HearID assumed area of 44 mm² (solid lines) and the areas measured at each location from the CT scan (dashed lines). The area A used to determine Z_o and thus the absorbance, not unexpectedly, has a larger effect when the canal's area is much larger than its assumed area (e.g., Subject 55). The assumption of a constant canal area across all subjects has the effect of reducing the population variability in low-frequency absorbance (< 1000-2000 Hz), which is heavily controlled by the canal area; as the area increases, this low frequency absorbance decreases. Thus, it appears that one effect of calculating absorbance from the measured canal area would be to increase the variability in absorbance across subjects. Once again, we are unsure how to interpret and to choose an appropriate canal area for absorbance calculations.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work provides anatomical measurements of the ear canal's geometry, including cross-sectional areas along its length, canal length, center spline curves representing canal curvature, and the area and location of the canal's first bend. Certain quantities, particularly at the more lateral areas, seem to correlate with age across the lifespan.

Measurements of impedance and absorbance with 3D-printed canals, incorporating real-ear anatomy coupled to an artificial ear, indicate that the nonuniform area and curvature of the canal contribute to variations in these WAI measurements, which are not fully understood. In particular, it is not clear what the characteristic impedance of the ear canal means in this context.

Some outcomes of this work could include:

1. An improved understanding of the anatomical developmental changes in the canal's structure during early childhood could help determine when hearing-aid molds should be updated due to canal growth.
2. Commercial WAI systems might consider employing an age-based canal area for the calculation of absorbance.
3. Recommendations for designing deeper-fitting probes to minimize variability in the canal's cross-sectional area.
4. Development of finite-element models of the canal from multiple subjects to investigate further how canal shape and area influence canal acoustics.
5. Modifications to transmission-line based models for ear-canal acoustics with a modified description of quantities such as the characteristic impedance.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Allen, Jont: The scale for the magnitude of the absorbance and reflectance should be put on a decibel scale because then you have an objective measure of loudness changes. I suspect that if you put these on a decibel scale you will find changes on the order of a few dB and they will not be large enough to measure these changes psychophysically. *Response:* We plotted reflectance and absorbance on a linear scale because that is how the field is plotting it. The area that we use to calculate absorbance and admittance does appear to be important because it sets the low-frequency values of these quantities in ways that we might be ignoring.

Bergevin, Chris: Could you comment on what happens going the other way? Could you comment on how canal shape might affect quantities traveling in the reverse direction such as spontaneous otoacoustic emissions and why there may be so much variation across individuals? *Response:* Great question! I have not thought about how the canal shape could affect the reverse sound transmission. One thing I did not cover in my talk is that the further we can get the probe into the ear canal, there is less ear canal to affect the response and (shows figure 1 of talk) there is also a lot less variability in the area of the canal closer to the eardrum. Area starts changing more dramatically near the second bend, roughly 15 mm from the ear drum. The further we can insert our probes the better.

Ketton, Darlene: I'm curious about the fact that you are using an area at an arbitrary point. What about using the air volume at segments and in particular looking at the double bend in the upper ear and the single bend at the lower ear? You could pick a ratio between volumes in various segments and compare those. Also, are you using isotropic voxels in your scans? *Response:* I'm not sure what you are suggesting we would use the volume for. What do you want to know about the scans? **Ketton, Darlene:** What is the thickness of scans vs the dimensions you are using in your field of view? *Response:* The thickness of most scans is 0.4 mm so they are very high resolution; all scans are 0.4 to 0.75 mm in thickness. **Ketton, Darlene:** The reason I was bringing up volume is to use a ratio, a more complex metric, compound metric, rather than just cross-sectional area. *Response:* We measure in 1 and 2 mm increments and maybe that would be helpful to look at. Thank you. (Note, the area is what is important for wideband acoustic immittance measurements.)

Martin, Pascal: When sound comes to the outer ear it is focused to a smaller area and presumably increases pressure. It's important because it would change the energy flow, not the amount of energy, but a change in the efficiency of the transmission to the ear. With your model I guess you could check that. People have measured pressure near the eardrum and shown an increase in pressure, say 0 dB outside the canal and 9 dB at the tympanum. Can you check that in the model measuring pressure at the entrance and then test whether the shape is important, and then modify the shape and see how the transfer has changed. that because you can modify that and see how the transfer function has changed. *Response:* Do you mean using the entire outer ear? **Martin, Pascal:** You have a perfect model system and you don't have the inner ear. You just probe what is the importance of changing area and exact shape of your canal. But what we really care about is you know the input-output so for a given shape you could test what you get at the output for a given input. *Response:* Yes. We can do that and in our case, the entrance would be where the probe sits several mm into the ear. But you could imagine perhaps using a CT scan and printing a larger portion of the ear which I have not done and doing free field as well. So the answer is yes, you could put a little microphone down at the other end.

Hajicek, Joshua: It seems like there is a lot of focus on what is going on at the TM. But what about a distributed reflection from changes in area like when the wavefront goes in the opposite direction? *Response:* Sure, I agree. That is why we are trying to put our probe at different locations. It is also possible we could put probe microphones along the entire canal.

Boothalingam, Sriram: Written comments from before the MOH workshop. This is an excellent study that challenges the assumptions of sound absorption measures that are based on an ideal cylinder with static cross-sectional area. The data presented here are unique and can lead to significant improvements in the accuracy of ear canal and middle ear absorption measures.

- “Measurements were taken at 2 mm intervals, commencing at the tympanic annulus and shifting to 1 mm intervals either at 24 mm from the tympanic annulus or within a few mm of the first bend, whichever occurred first.” Is there a specific reason for this change in resolution of measurement? *Response:* This decision was

made because we were focused on the region of the first bend and each measurement at each location is time intensive.

- What bearing would the solid, presumably more reflective, walls of the 3D printed canals have on the results, relative to absorbance measured in a live ear that has skin, and possibly warm and moist? *Response: We have shown that the results in the 3D-printed canals are consistent with measurements made in artificial ears that meet ANSI standards; losses along the ear canal are generally considered negligible in adult ears but this question is a good one as we study ear canals of infants, which are far smaller in diameter than those of adults.*
- It is fantastic that the authors minimized variability of the middle ear by using the same artificial ear across all ear canals. However, I wonder to what extent the variability in absorbance reported here would be different if the ear canal models terminated with individualistic middle ear impedances. For instance, would it reduce or further increase between subject variability? *Response: Presumably we would measure more variability if the canals were terminated by different artificial ears. The reason we used the same artificial ear was to limit variability to only the ear canal.*
- It would be great if the authors could include a commentary on how applying a more accurate ear canal area in absorbance measurements would influence clinical decision making. The child vs. adult difference in area is obvious, but I mean among adults. *Response: The answer to this question is the reason we are making these measurements – we only have preliminary measurements for now but hope to answer this question after collecting and analyzing more measurements.*
- Some panels in Fig 2 are in boxes and some are not. Given this is a busy figure, losing the box might be visually appealing. Also, in panel C, there appears to be something funky about the box plot for superior position. *Response: The boxes are forced by Matlab and not easily undone so we will leave them. The box plot in panel C (superior position) has the median notch “flipped” back over on itself due to uncertainty in the true median value.*

Lovich, Stephanie: Written comments from before the MOH workshop. Common practice for measuring wide-band acoustic immittance hinges on an ear canal cross-sectional area that is circular. However, this assumption could lead to inaccurate measurements, especially across age ranges. This work is very interesting and could lead to much more precise clinical tools based on the size and shape of an individual patient’s ear canal.

- I am really interested in the range of measures you get in figure 1, especially in the older population (the dark red lines). I am excited to hear more about change in ear canal area over time, but also the variance you get in older populations versus younger populations. *This work comparing anatomical measurements over ears of all ages is ongoing and the topic of a different publication.*
- I am also very interested to hear more of your thoughts on variation in figure 5. Do these measures of curvature and area in these 3 subjects encompass the rest of the population? Or is the variance of curvature and area very large across subjects? *Response: We don’t have measurements in enough subjects to answer this question other than to say these 3 of 8 subjects were selected to be representative of the range among our 8 ears. Yes, there is a great deal of variability and we are still working on methods to describe that variability and so our explanations of it remain somewhat subjective.*
- What do you think is the most important feature of an off-the-shelf probe based on your data? Do they have to be customized to individuals or would a deeper probe suffice for most people? *Response: A deep fitting probe that sits near the medial end of the second bend (presumably about 12-18 mm from the tympanic membrane) seems like it would be ideal. It can be difficult to insert probes that deep in some canals, and it can also be difficult to get leak-free seals in some canals.*